

Recommended citation: Jensen, L. P. (2018). Is team performance in project-based PBL better if all team members have the same work ethic?. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 897-904). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672730.

Is team performance in project based PBL better if all team members have the same work ethic?

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Conference Key Areas: Recruitment and Retention, Educational and Organizational Development, Engineering Skills

Keywords: Peer Learning, Cooperation, Engineering Education, Retention

INTRODUCTION

All Engineering Educations at Aalborg University uses Problem Based Learning as learning method. On each semester, the students work in groups of 5-7 members on a 15 ECTS semester project supported by courses.

Groups with good communication and collaboration has a higher potential for peer learning and a successful sharing of knowledge than groups struggling to communicate and collaborate. A study in 2016 [1] showed that the most well organized and collaborative groups worked full time on the project at the University but also worked a lot on the project at home. Other groups preferred to do most project work at home and only meet at University for courses and a couple of meetings a week to discuss the progress of their project and assign new tasks. The well-organized groups used peer learning more than the other groups and received better marks.

These results was presented for students studying within IT in the beginning of their first semester 2017. In October, new groups was formed and the students used the

knowledge to form homogeneous groups where either all members wanted to work full time at the University or all members preferred to do most project work at home.

This paper investigates if these groups perform better with good communication, collaboration, and lower dropout rates than another cohort with less homogeneous groups, by analysing and comparing written process analysis from each group, average marks for the projects and student dropouts.

1 BACKGROUND

A study in 2016 [1] showed that first year student group at Aalborg University within IT studies could be categorized in three:

- A. **The well-organized group that shares knowledge and socialize:** “This group meets almost every day to discuss the project and its progress. The tasks are distributed both individual and sometimes in smaller groups. Although the group do most project work at the University, each group member also do a lot project work at home, communicating regularly with the other members. All knowledge gained in the project is shared by reading and discussing the documents produced. The group spirit is high and the group members meets outside University for sports, gaming, cinema, party, a beer, etc.”
- B. **The organized group that shares most knowledge:** “This group often uses Monday for planning project activities for the whole week. Specific tasks are distributed on an individual level and usually this work is done at home, communicating regularly with the other members. At University, the group uses the time to discuss the results of the performed tasks and the progress of the project. All documents is shared and usually read by all members, but in some groups there might be a few members not reading all documents. If there is something a member do not understand they can ask and the author will try to explain. The group spirit is not as high as in the A group. The group members do not socialize outside University”.
- C. **The unorganized group that do not communicate and share knowledge nor socialize neither at University or outside:** “This group is not organized formally and only meet after lectures to “give each other homework”. Then they go home and rest after the lecture. They do the individual homework with very little communication. They share the produced documents on e.g. Goggle Docs but it is only a few group members that read the documents and they do not discuss any documents. There is only informal review of the documents. The group spirit is low and although the members can make fun and fool around sometimes at the University they are not mates and do not socialize neither at the university nor outside”.

The study [1] investigated the hypothesis: “It seems obvious that groups with good communication and collaboration who is working most of the time in their group room has a higher potential for peer learning and a successful sharing of knowledge than

groups struggling to communicate and collaborate and often doing most of the project work individually at home”.

The results of the small study (74 students) proved the hypothesis right and the results from the project exam showed that groups labelled A generally received higher average marks than groups labelled B and C. Groups labelled C was generally receiving low average marks.

2 THE EXPERIMENT

The group classification from 1 was presented to the students of a new cohort starting in September 2017 to help them identify what kind of group they were in and be more aware of the consequences in terms of learning, collaboration and marks. After the presentation the students were asked which group they would like to be in and on an average individual level app. half of the students indicated by a quick show of hands that they thought they would prefer to be a member of an A group, and the other half would rather be in a B group. No students was attracted to the C group.

The first 1½ month the students are randomly placed in groups of 6-7 to work with a small project (5 ECTS) aiming at giving them a brief introduction to project work at Aalborg University and the first experiences of how to collaborate on a project and share knowledge. The experiences is analysed and reflected in each group and plans for improvement is made before they start on a longer project for the rest of the semester, app. two month (10 ECTS).

The group formation for the new project is handled by the students based on both interest for a specific project proposal and knowledge about the other students. The investigated cohort was all IT students but they had signed up for two different studies: **S**oftware **E**ngineering (SE - 127 students) and **C**omputer **S**cience (CS - 88 students). Each study has to form groups for the projects internally, but all of the students follow the same courses and share a team of supervisors to facilitate the individual groups. Before the group formation process the students study a catalogue of project proposals and each student has to type in the project proposal they prefer and then there is two hours where the students can meet with other students with the same interest in project proposals to discuss the project and form groups.

The SE student had to form no more than 19 groups and the CS students 12 groups. Most of the project proposals had been chosen by more than 10 students so more than one group could be formed based on each project proposal. This made it possible for the students to form groups based on other topics: work load, ambition, work method etc.

Some of the first SE students that typed in their selected project proposal also typed their preference for which type of group they wanted to be in and many of the other SE students followed this idea. This information was used in the group formation process of the SE cohort to form groups were all members had a preference for either the type A group or the type B group. The CS students didn't type in their group preference so it is expected that more groups were formed where some students

preferred to work as a type A group and other to work as a type B group, which potentially might lead to conflicts about where and how to work on the project.

It was decided to investigate if the SE groups performed better with better communication, collaboration, and lower dropout rates than the CS cohort did.

3 METHOD

The two cohorts of students will be compared by analysing a written process analysis, the average mark for the projects and student dropouts from each group.

3.1 Process analysis

The process analysis is a shared written document where each group right after handing in their project report write and reflect about what happened in the group when working with the project, why it happened and how to improve the performance in the next project. Each group have to analyse how they have collaborated and solved eventual conflicts, how they have planned and controlled the project and how they have shared and helped each other to learn all the knowledge produced.

These written documents was analysed to find out which classification (see 1) each group belonged to and if they have used peer learning when sharing knowledge from the project.

Feedback is provided for the groups on their process analysis. A teacher comments in writing the quality and fulfilment of the learning goals for the process analysis and write some questions and comments to help the students reflect deeper. No marks are given but the teacher noted down the mark he would give for the quality of each process analysis to be used as data for comparing the groups in each classification.

3.2 Average marks for projects

The results of the project work from each group is documented in a project report and the process analysis. Both documents is a part of the project exam where each group starts presenting the results of their project and process. Then questions is asked to each student to test the knowledge about the different project subjects and there is a discussion with all students participating about the methods and theories used, the pro and con's and lessons learned. Based on both written documents (project report and process analysis), and each students performance during presentation, questioning and discussion, individual marks are given for each student.

The marks for each student in each SE and CS group is collected to calculate the group average marks. To be able to identify each group according to the classification made using the process analysis the group number is known but not written to keep anonymity of the groups.

3.3 Student drop out

This paper is comparing the behaviour of two cohorts of students working in groups with a big project (10 ECTS) running for two month. Concerning drop out is it interesting how many student that leaves their group during the project period.

Some students leave their group because they don't want to continue their study, so they officially stop studying and is registered as "drop outs". In some groups conflicts between the group members about how the project work should be done becomes so big that a group member leaves the group to become an individual student either voluntarily or forced out as a result of a counselling with the supervisor.

The number of drop outs can be extracted from official statistics and the number of individual students enrolled for exam at the end of the semester can be found in the exam plan.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Process analysis

The results from the analysis of the process analysis can be seen in *Table 1* for the Software Engineering students and in *Table 2* for the Computer Science students. Many of the groups had labelled them self as A groups and some as B groups (see 1). Several groups had invented an extra classification in their analysis: a group that like group A preferred to be working at the University almost full time, but could see some benefits by having one or two days a week where they worked at home. This category is labelled A light. No groups labelled them self a C group but from their own description of group behaviour it was possible to identify a few C groups in each cohort.

Table 1. Number of SE groups in each classification (see 1), their use of Peer Learning and marks for quality of their process analysis

Classification	Groups SE		P.L. %	Marks in Danish 7-step and European ECTS scale						
	number	%		12/A	10/B	7/C	4/D	2/E	0/Fx	Av.
A	10	53	100	2	2	4	2			5,8/C
A light	4	21	100	1		2	1			7,5/C
B	3	16	33			1	1		1	3,7/D
C	2	11	0					1	1	1,0/E-F

Table 2. Number of CS groups in each classification (see 1), their use of Peer Learning and marks for quality of their process analysis

Classification	Groups CS		P.L. %	Marks in Danish 7-step and European ECTS scale						
	number	%		12/A	10/B	7/C	4/D	2/E	0/Fx	Av.
A	7	58	100	1	1	3	2			7,3/C
A light	2	17	100			1	1			5,5/C
B	1	8	100					1		2/E
C	2	17	0				1	1		3,0/D-E

The results from the two cohorts shows that although the SE students used the group classification deliberately to form homogeneous groups when it comes to preferences about how when and where to work on the project, the CS groups also ended up being quite homogeneous. In both cohorts the A and A light groups all used peer learning when sharing knowledge and ended up with good and high marks for the quality of the process analysis whereas the B and C groups only use peer learning in one B group in each cohort and all except for this group in the SE cohort ended up with low marks for the process analysis.

4.2 Average marks for projects

The individual marks for the project exam for each group is converted and truncated into average marks on the Danish 7 step scale and the European ECTS scale. The results is presented in *Table 3* and *Table 4* for each of the classifications from *Table 1* and *Table 2*. The average of all groups in each classification is the average of the average group marks before truncation.

Table 3. Number of SE groups in each classification (see 1), their use of Peer Learning and average group marks for the project exam

Classification	Groups SE		P.L. %	Average Marks in Danish 7-step and European scale						
	number	%		12/A	10/B	7/C	4/D	2/E	0/Fx	Av.
A	10	53	100	3	5	2				9,5/B
A light	4	21	100		1	1	2			7,0/C
B	3	16	33		1		1		1	4,5/D
C	2	11	0				1	1		3,9/D

The results from the project exam of the SE students shown in *Table 3* clearly shows that the students from the A and A light group performed considerably better at the exam than the B and C groups which indicates that their project reports was better and they had learned more about the subjects from the projects. The one B group that used peer learning to share knowledge got a high mark.

Table 4. Number of CS groups in each classification (see 1), their use of Peer Learning and average group marks for the project exam

Classification	Groups CS		P.L. %	Average Marks in Danish 7-step and European scale						
	number	%		12/A	10/B	7/C	4/D	2/E	0/Fx	Av.
A	7	58	100		3	3	1			8,2/C
A light	2	17	100		1		1			7,7/C
B	1	8	100		1					8,8/B
C	2	17	0				1	1		3,85/D

The results from the project exam of the CS students shown in *Table 4* shows that the students from the A and A light and the B group performed considerably better at the exam than the C groups which indicates that their project reports was better and they had learned more about the subjects from the projects.

4.3 Student drop out

From the official statistics counting students every month the development in the number of SE and CS students is found: How many started in groups, stopped during the semester and the final number enrolled for exam. From the exam lists the number of students in a group for the exam and the number of individual student is found. All this information is presented in *Table 5*.

Table 5. Development in number of students in SE groups and CS groups during the semester, both in total numbers and in percentage of number of starting students

Study	Number of students						Numbers in %		
	Starting in groups Nov. 1 st	Stopped between Nov. 1 st Jan. 2 nd	Enrolled for exam Jan. 2 nd	Individual students Jan. 2 nd (exam)	In group Jan.2 nd (exam)	Left group during sem.	Stopped during semester	Individual students	Total left group
SE	127	5	122	5	117	10	3,9	3,9	7,8
CS	88	6	82	5	77	11	6,8	5,7	12,5

Table 5 shows that app. the same number of students (5-6) in each of the two cohorts has stopped studying officially (dropped out) during the semester and during the same period a similar number of students has left their group to continue the semester as individual students. The SE cohort has app. 50 % more students as the CS cohort, so the percentage of students leaving a group is lower in the SE cohort than in the CS cohort. To find out if the difference in the percentage of drop out students is a special case for these cohorts the drop out rate is collected from statistics for the previous four years (see *Table 6*), using the total number of students from the IT school as reference.

Table 6. Drop out rate in percent for all students from the IT school, Software Engineering and Computer Science students from 2013 to 2017

Study	2017	2016	2015	2014	2013
IT school total	5,4	6,8	7,1	7,3	8,1
Software Eng.	3,9	7,9	7,8	1,9	8,3
Computer Sci.	6,8	7,6	17,3	12,1	13,7

Table 6 shows that during the 4 years before 2017 both SE and CS has a higher drop out rate than the average for the whole IT school, except for SE in 2014 where students from another study was allowed to change to SE during the semester. In 2017 both SE and CS has a lower drop out than usual indicating that the more homogeneous groups is better for the retention of students.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Based on the results from the process analysis (4.1) and the average marks for projects (4.2) there is more similarities than differences between the two cohorts of students. This proves the expectation from 2 about differences in student preference for A or B group in the SE and CS cohort wrong, so the experiment has failed to prove SE groups more homogeneous than CS groups.

The reason for this could be that the CS groups have used their knowledge about the group classification when forming groups although they didn't put their preferences in writing before the group formation and they probably also was inspired by the SE students.

Only the drop out rates (4.3) shows the expected difference between SE and CS students, but if we go back in time there is a tendency that CS has higher drop out rates than SE students.

Interestingly the number of A and A light groups in both cohorts is 75 % which is considerably higher than the students own expectation for preference shown by raise of hands in the start of the semester (50 %) and the results from the previous study [1] showing 50 % A groups. This is indicating that the information about group classification in the beginning of the semester have had an impact in the students consciousness about that using more time for project work at the University pays of in terms of better group collaboration, group spirit, peer learning and marks.

The conclusion of the paper is that although the expected difference in SE and CS groups has failed to show the number of A and A light groups in both cohorts has grown and they get better marks than half of the B and all C groups, which is strengthening the proof of the hypothesis (see 1) from [1]. The procedure of presenting the group classification for the students at the start of the first semester will therefore be continued and if possible expanded by more formal procedures for using the classification as a part of the group forming process. The intention is to promote that the students form groups based on both interest of project proposals and what kind of group they want to be in according to the classification.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jensen, L.P. (2016), Collaboration and Peer Learning in Problem Based Learning, *44th Annual SEFI Conference, Tampere Finland*.